

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF HOSPITALS IN BULGARIA - SITUATION AND PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

What is presented in this article are data on the number and distribution of state and municipal hospitals and the beds in them. Bulgaria has a dense network of hospitals - a total of 241 by 2022, including state, municipal and private medical establishments. The total number of hospitals hasn't changes significantly in the past 10 years, but the number of beds in them has been raising gradually from 47 thousand to 54 thousand in 2022. Bulgaria's hospital structure is characterised by overcapacity that isn't reflective of the population's realised need for hospital treatment. The hospital infrastructure available is unevenly distributed across the country's territory, with an over-concentration of hospital structures in the largest cities and a insufficient capacity for satisfying the basic hospitalisation needs in the smaller province centres.

Keywords: state hospitals, municipal hospitals, number, distribution, beds.

INTRODUCTION

Hospital healthcare is the most complex sector in the healthcare system. Hospitals continue to increase many and varied problems despite a series of reforms and changes in search of better and more efficient solutions [4,5]. Regardless of the fact that the priority of any progress in the last 30 years continues to improve the access of Bulgarian citizens to qualified medical care, as well as the increase in the improvement of medical services in practice is not happening [1].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The purpose of this article is to analyze the number and distribution of state and municipal hospitals in our country for the period 2011-2022.

To realize this goal, the following tasks have been completed:

1. Analysis of normative documents regulating the structure, distribution and activity of medical facilities for hospital medical care.
2. Analysis of the number of medical facilities for inpatient care and beds in them for the period 2011-2022.

The following research methods were used: comparative analysis, documentary method, graphic method for visualizing the obtained results. Various regulatory documents, reporting documents from the NHIF, reports and strategies have been studied.

RESULTS DISCUSSION

Hospitals in Bulgarian are registered as trade companies in accordance with the requirements of trade act, and as such have to follow all requirements of the trade legislations, such as accounting, deadlines, documentation and information availability. It follows that their accounting documents should be available for access

by the public to look at and analyse in the Trade Register.

Medical establishments for hospital care in our country are defined in Article 9 of the Medical Establishment Act as hospitals for active treatment, hospitals for continuous treatment, rehabilitations hospitals, hospitals for continuous treatment and rehabilitation. They can be multi-profiled or specialised [10]. Their activity is also regimented in detail in Chapter 4 of the same act. Legislation determines the availability requirements for national and regional hospital maps, which indicate the place and manner of hospital health services needed by the population. The location of hospitals across the territory of the country is chosen based on these maps.

Under the current legislation and the concept for health care system development, health services within the scope of hospital care are structured into the following 3 levels, as follows [9]:

The first level of hospital service has a predominantly local character. The second level of hospital service has a predominantly regional character. The third level of hospital service has a predominantly national character. At that level, in addition to the activities at the third and second level, there are a specialised and ultraspecialised hospital services, which include activities in the scope of all medical specialities, including the incorporation of new medical technologies for diagnostics and treatment, diagnosing and treating rare illnesses, medical scientific research, etc.

The populations hospital care needs are planned for in the Nation Health Map of Bulgaria at the regional and national level. The indicator used is the internationally recognised measure of capacity - "1 hospital bed", which has been used in developing of the currently used

National Health Map. Bulgarian legislation clearly defines a hospital bed (by types and medical specialities) as a measure of capacity, including the activities conducted on it, as well as the requirements for a hospital bed, according to the established medical standards, including personnel, the medical equipment, spaces, organisations, etc. needed for the activity that guarantee the activity's quality. I.e. after determining the needed number of beds for conducting a particular activity, based on the all the resources, be they human or material, for its realisation can be planned for [6,7,8].

In line with to the adopted regulations on the structure and content of the regional and National Health Maps and the approved Methodology for the development of the Regional Health Maps, the concrete needs for hospital beds and medical activities are planned at the district level according to type and level of competence of the respective structures for all districts, as well as the types of medical activities to be planned at the regional level. The hospital services needs and the capacity needed for their satisfaction, using this methodology, is determined first at the local level, and then the capacity needed for these activities is planned for at the regional and national level based on the levels of hospital service.

The hospital health map currently mostly covers the medical establishments for hospital care that are present, and does not recommend closing excess capacity (the legislation also doesn't set out to determine the capacity as either sufficient or excessive). There is not enough exact information on healthcare not only on the supply but also on demand, which could provide the opportunity for analysing capacity and taking appropriate decisions. According to the newest data by Eurostat Bulgaria has the largest number of hospital beds in the EU compared to the population with 792.3 beds per 100

000 people, whereby the average for the EU is 524.8 beds for 2021. According to the National Health Insurance Fund's information, the beds in use in hospitals rarely go over 50% capacity.

Hospitals in Bulgarian are registered as trade companies in accordance with the requirements of trade act, and as such have to follow all requirements of the trade legislations - for example: accounting, deadlines, documentation and information availability. This means that their accounting documents should be available for access by the public to look at and analyse in the Trade Register.

There is an important question regarding the ownership of capital in those trade companies. Depending on who owns the capital, the hospitals can be divided into state hospitals (in which case the capital is owned by the Ministry of Healthcare), municipal hospitals (in which case the capital is owned by a municipality) and private hospitals. This distinction is used in the current analysis, as at this stage we will not be touching on the private hospital care establishments [2,3].

The main activity performed by hospitals is the diagnostics and treatment of diseases. The majority of these activities are covered by the NHIF, and a minor part is paid directly by the patients, while an insignificant part of the financing received by hospitals comes from health insurance companies. Therefore, clinical pathways are the main tool used to finance the treatment of hospitalised patients [6].

Bulgaria has a dense network of hospitals - a total of 241 by 2022, including state, municipal and private medical establishments. The total number of hospitals hasn't changes significantly in the past 10 years, but the number of beds in them has been raising gradually from 47 thousand to 54 thousand in 2022 [10].

Figure 1. Number of hospitals and bed available in them for the 2011-2022 period.

Source: https://ime.bg/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/hospitals_ime.pdf

In 2022 there were 189 state and municipal hospitals functioning in Bulgaria. 68 were state hospitals, while 121 were municipal. There is a hospital in every of 28 Provinces and in 104 (out of 265) municipalities, usually in the municipality's center town. The majority of hospital is in the capital Sofia. There are seven in Varna, 6 in Plovdiv, five in Vratsa, Veliko Tarnovo and

Burgas. There are four hospitals in Haskovo, Stara Zagora, Ruse and Blagoevgrad, and 3 in Pernik. There are 2 hospitals in another 12 towns, and one in each of the remaining 81 towns [10].

The formation of health islands with more hospital care facilities around the capital and Pernik; around Vratsa, Burgas and Varna is of interest. For some of them, the well-developed network is explained by the legacy of state hospitals from the past, which are still

maintained today; by the presence of a medical university around which a whole plethora of medical establishments has been formed; and by purely geographical factors, which do not allow easy concentration of patients. However, the municipalities that lack public hospitals are of greater interest - those around Plovdiv and Pazardzhik, in Dobrudja around Dobrich and Varna, in northwestern Bulgaria, whose residents travel to Vratsa and most probably to the capital when they require hospital treatment [7]. These are most often municipalities that either have a limited population, or are situated in proximity to larger municipalities or province centers.

CONCLUSION:

Bulgaria's hospital structure is characterised by overcapacity that isn't reflective of the population's realised need for hospital treatment. The hospital infrastructure available is unevenly distributed across the country's territory, with an overconcentration of hospital structures in the largest cities and a insufficient capacity for satisfying the basic hospitalisation needs in the smaller province centres. The current structuring of the hospital beds is ineffective, with a pre beds for active treatment being predominant, while the availability of beds for long-term care is extremely low. According to R. Grozdanova [1], restructuring the hospital sector would require active policy targeted at overcoming the growing imbalances in the population's access to hospital care in the smaller settlements and the over-concentration of hospital capabilities in specific centres by mechanising the National Health Map and incorporating effective regulations for the process of opening new hospitals and hospitalisation structures. Neglecting

these problems and postponing adequate government action for their resolution has an extremely adverse impact on the development of the health care system, and consequently on the long-term health of the citizens.

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